

UNDERPIN

DATA SPACE FOR MANUFACTURING

Pan-European Data Space for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries

D3.2 UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure, final deployment and integration report

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AP	Authority Portal
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous integration/continuous development
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (dissemination level)
CORS	Cross-Origin Resource Sharing
CSV	Comma separated value
D2.2	UNDERPIN Deliverable D2.2: Requirements Specification
D3.1	UNDERPIN Deliverable D3.1: Mid-Term Deployment and Integration Report
D3.2	UNDERPIN Deliverable D3.2: Final Deployment and Integration Report
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DSP	Dataspace Protocol
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana
FQDN	fully qualified domain name
HPA	Horizontal Pod Autoscaler
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	HTTP Secure
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
JWT	JSON Web Token
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
mTLS	Mutual Transfer Layer Security
OAuth2	Open Authorization 2.0
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
PP	Restricted to other program participants (dissemination level)
PU	Public (dissemination level)
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control

RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (dissemination level)
REST	Representational State Transfer
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SEN	Limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement (dissemination level)
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
TLS	Transport layer security
UI	User Interface
URI	Uniform resource identifier
URL	Uniform resource locator
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
XACML	eXtensible Access Control Markup Language
XAI	Explainable AI

1. Introduction

The UNDERPIN project lays the groundwork for a pan-European Data Space infrastructure for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries. The present deliverable (D3.2) describes the final deployment and integration of the UNDERPIN platform in November 2025 after an iterative development cycle of 24 months. This infrastructure responds to a significant industrial challenge of fragmented operational data across / at the edge of organizational and technology boundaries that can empower, among other use cases, predictive maintenance and collaborative optimization amongst operators, equipment manufacturers and maintenance providers.

The UNDERPIN infrastructure is built upon IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) and GAIA-X standards but develops manufacturing domain-specific solutions. The key infrastructure components - the Authority Portal for participant onboarding, the DAPS (Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service) for federated identity management across various environments, the EDC (Eclipse Dataspace Connector) for policy-driven data exchange, a federated blockchain for immutable auditing, time-series databases for time-series analytics and semantic technologies for interoperability - were combined into an integrated, production-ready platform. The deployment phase (months 12-24) encountered and addressed issues related to technology maturity challenges, integration of multiple components and coordination of multiple teams across multiple institutions. Insights from the deployment phase are described and denoted as relevant for other Data Space infrastructure projects.

1.1 Purpose and scope

D3.2 delivers an in-depth technical description of the deployed UNDERPIN infrastructure, providing a record of the successful implementations, the issues faced, the workarounds used, and insights gained. It covers all tasks associated with WP3: deployment of enabler (T3.2), establishment of a smart contract framework (T3.3), interoperability of Data Space through semantic technology (T3.4) and dry-run testing with validation of operational readiness (T3.5). Part of the report specifically refers to the integration complexity with third-party systems; in particular, the Authority Portal developed by Sovity and the EDC ecosystem, all of which raised issues regarding component maturity; thus, involving a phased approach to resolution over time. This provides a baseline operational state for measuring future evolution and upgrades, whilst justifiably redacting sensitive information related to security while maintaining architectural transparency.

1.2 Structure of the document

Following this introduction, the report is structured as follows: Section 2 gives an overview of platform architecture including the establishment of the four-layered data architecture and its alignment with the principles of the IDS Reference Architecture Model. Sections 3-8 cover the major components of the infrastructure in functional order i.e. Authority Portal (Section 3), DAPS (Section 4), EDC Connector (Section 5), Blockchain Node (Section 6), Time-series Database (Section 7) and Metadata Management (Section 8). Section 9 covers operational maintenance and monitoring of the infrastructure including Prometheus, Grafana, alerts and the ELK (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana) stack for centralized logging. Section 10 concludes the report with lessons learned and recommendations. Appendices include deployment configurations for EDC and the Authority Portal (Appendix A-B) and examples of integration test cases and results

(Appendix C). Throughout, relevant cross-references to D2.2 (UNDERPIN Deliverable D2.2: Requirements Specification) and D3.1 (UNDERPIN Deliverable D3.1: Mid-Term Deployment and Integration Report) will be included when referring to architectural decisions that implement requirements or build upon progress.

2. Platform Architecture

2.1 UNDERPIN Component-level Architecture

The UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure implements a modular, sovereign architecture aligned with the project's D2.2 requirements. It adheres to International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) principles via Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC), ensuring secure, interoperable data exchange across manufacturing partners.

2.1.1 Core Components

The Authority Portal acts as the primary access point for data discovery, contract negotiation and administrative activities. It is hosted on Kubernetes with Helm and integrates the Catalog Crawler (Metadata Broker) while maintaining fine-grained access control as defined in D2.2 Sec. 3.2 and enabling CORS (Cross-Origin Resource Sharing) on the Elasticsearch instance to allow for seamless API (Application Programming Interface) communications. The Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) implements authentication, authorization and attribute issuing according to D2.2 Sec. 4.1, securing endpoints via Keycloak while using the Vault which is available only for consortium partners. The EDC Connector enables policy-based sovereign data transfer between participants, with each connector operating on Kubernetes as an independent microservice, both configured to utilize tolerations and nodeSelectors in its Helm Chart while allowing for clients to remain highly available, by not being coupled to a single connector deployment. The blockchain node provides an immutable ledger facilitating smart-contract execution and audit trails, integrating with the EDC UI (User Interface) to surface on-chain events, which further supports automatic smart-contract enforcement consistent with D2.2 Sec. 5.3. The centralized time-series database, using InfluxDB, stores sensor streams in addition to predictive analytics inputs, with buckets and authorization provisioned via Keycloak integration.

Metadata is enhanced and made discoverable by supporting Metadata Ingestor and Catalog Crawler deployments, which continuously populate the Metadata Broker according to D2.2 Sec. 6.2. Standardized ontologies and data schemas hosted in the Vocabulary Hub ensure semantic interoperability, incorporating domain-specific vocabularies as outlined in D2.2.

2.1.2 Integration and Interoperability

The architecture separates concerns across four layers, beginning with raw data ingestion where CSV (Comma Separated Value) files, APIs and predictive services feed into MinIO and InfluxDB after column names are sanitized and unified. Analytics engines, metadata ingestion pipelines and smart-contract logic in the service layer run as containerized workloads deployed in line with D2.2 Sec. 7.1. Secure data exchange is achieved in the integration layer via EDC and DAPS APIs, with every service exposing standardized REST (Representational State Transfer) endpoints that conform to IDSA metadata profiles. Finally, dashboards in Grafana and the Authority Portal UI render data visualizations and manage contracts, closing the loop from raw data through analysis, policy enforcement and presentation.

2.2 Cloud Infrastructure Deployment

The platform is deployed as a cloud-native solution on Kubernetes, following Infrastructure as Code practices to meet D2.2 Sec. 8.1 requirements.

2.2.1 Cluster and Environment

All components run in a dedicated K8s (Kubernetes) cluster on Hetzner, configured with Helm charts and GitOps pipelines. Nodes are distributed across availability zones to ensure resilience and comply with high-availability requirements. MinIO uses stateful sets with PersistentVolumeClaims; InfluxDB data is stored in PVCs (Persistent Volume Claims) with automated backups.

2.2.2 Networking and Security

Istio manages encrypted mTLS (Mutual Transfer Layer Security) traffic between microservices, enforcing network policies. Kubernetes RBAC (Role-Based Access Control) tightly controls access to namespaces and secrets. Vault policies restrict secret access to consortium roles. Prometheus alert rules have been implemented to trigger notifications on K8s component errors, automating issue detection and Grafana dashboards visualize system health.

2.2.3 Operational Upkeep

Horizontal Pod Autoscalers adjust replicas based on CPU/memory and custom metrics to cater for automated scaling and GitHub Actions build, test and deploy Helm charts for each component to support seamless CI/CD (Continuous integration/continuous development). Velero backs up cluster state and persistent volumes nightly. This deployment approach satisfies both the D2.2 requirements and all completed infrastructure issues, ensuring a robust, secure and scalable Data Space platform.

3. Authority Portal

3.1 Authority Portal description and features

As defined in D2.2 Section 3.2, the Authority Portal implements fine-grained access control mechanisms and integrates with the Catalog Crawler (Metadata Broker) to enable data discovery, contract negotiation, and administrative tasks. Metadata management aligns with D2.2 Section 6.2 requirements, where the Authority Portal serves as the primary interface for registering data assets and managing their semantic descriptions. The Authority Portal (AP) is the principal web interface for UNDERPIN Data Space participants. It enables:

- **Data Discovery:** A searchable catalog of shared assets, with filters on semantic metadata, provider and data type. The Catalog Crawler ensures metadata freshness.
- **Contract Management:** Initiation, negotiation and execution of usage contracts. Interacts with the EDC Connector control plane to automate policy negotiation and records finalized contracts on the blockchain ledger.
- **Administrative Functions:** Role-based user and attribute management via DAPS and Keycloak. Vault access is restricted to consortium partners to protect sensitive credentials.

- **Monitoring Dashboards:** Embedded Grafana and Kibana views for tracking data transfers, contract statuses and service health. CORS is enabled on Elasticsearch to support cross-origin dashboard embedding.

3.2 Deployment

Cloud infrastructure deployment follows D2.2 Section 8.1 specifications for Kubernetes-based deployment with Helm charts, ensuring scalable and resilient infrastructure. The AP is deployed using a Helm chart that provisions four components:

- **ap-frontend:** A React single-page application served by NGINX Ingress.
- **ap-backend:** A Spring Boot service providing REST APIs for catalog queries, contract operations and admin functions.
- **catalog-crawler:** The Metadata Broker service for metadata synchronization.
- **ap-database:** A PostgreSQL database for the ap-backend.

Key Helm values in values.yaml:

- ingress.hosts.host: ap.dataspace.underpinproject.eu
- edc.controlPlane.url: https://ap.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/
- daps.tokenEndpoint: https://daps.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/
- elasticsearch.cors.enabled: true

Horizontal Pod Autoscalers maintain 2–5 replicas based on CPU > 70%.

3.3 Access Control and Security

Authentication & Authorization provisions are handled utilizing OAuth2 (Open Authorization 2.0) via Keycloak; user claims and attributes are issued by DAPS per D2.2 Sec. 4.1. To this end, Kubernetes-managed Vault restricts secret access to authorized consortium roles. Moreover, all API traffic uses TLS with cert-manager-rotated certificates. Istio enforces mutual TLS (mTLS) and network segmentation between AP and other microservices. Unauthorized API requests are denied through appropriate messaging, enhancing UX and security clarity.

4. DAPS

4.1 DAPS description and features

The Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) provides centralized identity management, authentication and attribute issuance for all Data Space participants, as required by D2.2 Section 4.1. Key features include:

- **OAuth2 and OpenID Connect Support:** Issues JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) for client authentication and authorization.

- **Attribute Management:** Dynamically issues user and client attributes based on organization roles defined in consortium policies.
- **Federated Identity:** Integrates with external identity providers to support single sign-on across partner infrastructures.
- **Audit and Compliance:** Logs all token issuance and attribute assignments for traceability and regulatory reporting.

4.2 Deployment and Configuration

DAPS is deployed as a highly available microservice within Kubernetes using a Helm chart as per D2.2 Section 8.1 cloud infrastructure requirements. Two replicas of the DAPS service are deployed behind an NGINX ingress controller.

- **Configuration Values** (values.yaml):
 - keycloak.url: <https://daps.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/>
 - vault.address: <https://vault.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/>
 - vault.policies: List of Vault policies restricting secret access to consortium roles
 - Token.ttl: 30 min (default time-to-live for issued JWTs)

The Helm chart provisions a Spring Boot application that interfaces with Keycloak and Vault for DAPS-backend and a PostgreSQL database storing client registrations and issued attribute metadata as DAPS-db.

PersistentVolumeClaims back the database and cert-manager automates TLS certificates for the ingress. Horizontal Pod Autoscaler scales daps-backend replicas based on CPU usage above 60%.

4.3 Access Control and Security

Secrets (client credentials, encryption keys) are stored in Vault and accessed by DAPS only with tightly scoped Vault policies. Kubernetes RBAC ensures only authorized service accounts can modify DAPS resources. All external and internal endpoints enforce TLS, with mTLS between DAPS and downstream services. For Logging and Monitoring purposes Prometheus collects metrics on token issuance rates and error counts. Alerting rules notify on anomalous activity or component failures. All above features and configurations align with D2.2 requirements, as set in Section 4.1.

5. EDC Connector

Connector description and features

The Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) serves as the core data exchange mechanism within the UNDERPIN Data Space, implementing sovereign, policy-driven data transfers in compliance with IDSA and Dataspace Protocol standards per D2.2 Section 2.3. Based on D3.1 implementation, the connector operates on the EDC Community Edition (edc-ce) framework with the following features:

- **Automated Contract Negotiation:** Supports machine-readable usage policies enabling programmatic negotiation between data providers and consumers.
- **Policy-Based Access Control:** Enforces XACML (eXtensible Access Control Markup Language) - based policies at both control and data planes as specified in D2.2 Section 5.2.
- **Data Plane Separation:** Maintains strict architectural separation between control messages and data transfers to ensure governance isolation.
- **Protocol Adapters:** Includes HTTP(S) (Hypertext Transfer Protocol, secure), S3 (MinIO) and Kafka adapters for diverse data sources, with Kafka adapter added in D3.1 Section 3.6.
- **Transfer History:** Provides comprehensive audit trails of all data exchanges for compliance and monitoring purposes.

5.1 Deployment and Configuration

The EDC Connector is deployed as Kubernetes microservices using Helm charts with specific customizations documented in UNDERPIN D3.1

Deployment Units (per D3.1 Section 3.3.1):

- **edc-backend:** EDC Community Edition with resource limits: 2 CPU cores, 4GB RAM
- **edc-ui:** Connector management interface with Material-UI components
- **auth-proxy:** OAuth2 authentication proxy for securing management endpoints
- **postgresql:** Database backend for connector state and transfer history

Helm Chart Configuration (values.yaml):

- `connector.tolerations` and `connector.nodeSelectors`: Schedule on dedicated worker nodes for high availability
- `edc.participant.id`: Unique connector identifier registered in DAPS (e.g., MDSL1234XX.C1234XX)
- `Edc.management.endpoint`:
`https://<connector_name>.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/api/management`
- `edc.protocol.endpoint`:
`https://<connector_name>.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/api/dsp`
- Resource requests/limits updated per D3.1 Section 5.2: CPU 1-2 cores, Memory 2-4GB

Environment Variables (D3.1 Section 3.3.4):

- `MY_EDC_FQDN`: `<connector_name>.dataspace.underpinproject.eu`
- `EDC_OAUTH_TOKEN_URL`: `https://daps.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/`
- `EDC_KEYSTORE`: Path to .jks certificate file

- EDC_API_AUTH_KEY: The management API key

5.2 Sovity Components Upgrade Process

To maintain security, compatibility, access to new features and compliance with D2.2 Section 2.3 standards while addressing component maturity and integration requirements, the UNDERPIN consortium has implemented a coordinated upgrade process for Sovity-provided components.

A complete staging environment has been deployed under the staging-dataspace namespace with URLs under staging.dataspace.underpinproject.eu subdomain for testing upgrades before production deployment. Sovity provided technical assistance during upgrade windows to minimize disruptions and ensure smooth transitions

Staging Environment Components (deployed for upgrade testing):

- Staging Authority Portal: <https://ap.staging.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/>
- Staging DAPS: <https://daps.staging.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/>
- Staging Catalog Crawler: <http://crawler.staging.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/>
- Staging Keycloak: <https://keycloak.staging.dataspace.underpinproject.eu/>

Completed Upgrades:

- **Authority Portal:** Upgraded from v4.1.4 to v4.1.5 following Sovity documentation
- **Keycloak:** Major version upgrade to v26.0.7 with corresponding PostgreSQL database upgrade
- **Catalog Crawler:** Maintained compatibility with existing version while preparing for v5.0.0/v6.0.0 upgrade path

5.3 Tests for Sovity Components

To integrate Sovity components a testing framework was established. End-to-end workflows were tested between provider/consumer connectors using test policies for contract negotiation. We validated data transfer for HTTP and S3 adapter transfers. Error handling tests were performed confirming proper denial and audit logging. Tests were also run in "edc-integration-tests" stage with automated reporting. Finally, dedicated test cases validate functionality after component upgrades to ensure no regression in custom modifications.

Test results demonstrated successful policy enforcement and data plane isolation as required by D2.2 Section 5.3.

5.4 Enabling Cross-Origin Resource Sharing on the ElasticSearch instance in the K8S cluster

CORS configuration is implemented to support Authority Portal and dashboard integration:

Elasticsearch Configuration (version 7.17.3):

http.cors.enabled: true

http.cors.allow-origin: "*"

http.cors.allow-methods: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS

http.cors.allow-headers: Authorization, Content-Type

Security Measures:

- IP whitelisting restricts access to authorized cluster networks
- Basic authentication with service account credentials
- TLS encryption for all Elasticsearch communications
- Network policies isolate Elasticsearch pods within dedicated namespace

This configuration enables the Authority Portal's Data Catalog and Grafana dashboards to query connector metadata while maintaining security boundaries established in D3.1 deployment, in compliance with D2.2 Section 12.

6. Blockchain-backed Logging House

6.1 Logging House Architecture

The principal role of the blockchain-based network in the project is to serve as a logging house that fits into the Data Space architecture. The reference architecture of the International Data Spaces commonly uses the term clearing house but like in UNDERPIN the role of this component is often seen to be mostly passive, with a focus on recording events that occur in the Data Space. The term logging house is employed to emphasise on that. Since we heavily rely on the Eclipse Dataspace Components, the integration of the logging house in that environment was an important point in the design of the architecture and also its functionality.

Figure 1 -Architecture of the blockchain-backed logging house

The logging house consists of four different kinds of components:

Ethereum clients form an Ethereum network where a machine that runs the client software is called Ethereum node, or blockchain node. We use Hyperledger Besu¹ because of its support for private networks with Proof-of-Authority. As the burden for setting up a connector with all the required components should be relatively low for a participant, installing one's own Ethereum client was designed to be optional. There is at least one central instance that serves as a bootnode and at least two more nodes should be run in production to form a resilient network. Every participant will need an Ethereum account to be able to write records to the blockchain.

The **Agreement Smart Contract** is deployed on the Ethereum network and provides the basic functionality of the logging house. It defines which information is stored and in which order and by which party it is expected. It is written in Solidity, which is one of the most popular languages for writing smart contracts.

Every instance of the EDC Connector in the Data Space will be bundled with the **EDC logging house extension**, which is responsible for the communication between a connector and the Ethereum network. The contact point will be one specific Ethereum node, the local one if it exists or the bootnode being the default choices. To be able to handle an outage of one node, one or more fallback nodes can be configured. The extension handles the account information, most importantly the private key. The code is written in Java and makes use of the Web3j library². The EDC Connector already defines multiple events, which an extension can listen to for triggering custom code. In our case, this is used to send write or read requests to an Ethereum node. The

¹ <https://besu.hyperledger.org>

² <https://www.web3j.com/web3j-sdk>

logging house extension also comes with a UI integration to provide the possibility to view Blockchain records in the UI. There is only the possibility to view one's own records. While the records of other participants are not strictly secret, this information is not considered to be relevant.

The central instance of the Ethereum client can locally be accessed via the **Blockchain API**. This is intended as a means for an administrator to verify records of the blockchain without restricting the read access to the records created by one account only. It is a web server written in Haskell that provides a REST API.

6.2 Smart Contract Functionality

Figure 2 - Interactions with the Agreement Smart Contract

The smart contract describes the state of an agreement between provider and customer. Thereby, it closely follows the rules for agreements and data exchanges put in place by the EDC Connector. Adapting the smart contract this way allows a very good interoperability between the two components. The EDC Connector defines identifiers for contracts (*contractAgreementId*) and for data transfers (*transferProcessId*). A transfer is only possible if there is a valid contract. There can even be multiple transfers of the same contract, which in the simple case corresponds to repeated downloads of the same data.

Every contract conclusion marks an important point in the interaction between provider and customer. The majority of the smart contract functionality describes the phase after the

conclusion is reached to record the transactions which have to comply with the terms of the agreement. There are four main events that are reflected on the smart contract:

Accept contract: The provider can define all the terms of the contract upfront, possibly also restricting the list of customers. When a customer accepts a contract, it can thus immediately become a concluded contract. The smart contract doesn't mirror or enforce all of the terms of the contract, but it does so with the timespan within which the customer is allowed to download the data. The strategy put in place is to mirror this constraint without enforcing it. Thus, a malfunction of the EDC Connector that allowed a transaction at a time not within the access period won't be prohibited but recorded as such on the blockchain.

Log access request: An access request of the customer is recorded on the blockchain with a given *contractAgreementId* and *transferProcessId*. This requires that a valid contract is already in place.

Log transfer start: When the provider starts sending data, it will also log this event via the smart contract. With the EDC Connector a provider defines its own *transferProcessId* which won't be identical to the *transferProcessId* of the customer.

Log exchange: When a data transfer is finalised, both customer and provider create a record of that event. In the normal case this state should always be reached for a transaction, and the users can verify via the UI that the extension provides that the blockchain records are consistent with the behaviour of their EDC Connector instance.

7. Central Time-series database

7.1 Time-series database description and features

The project's use cases are centered around the use of sensory data, for which the optimal storage and querying solution is a time-series database. In order to alleviate the technical burden of existing and new Data Space participants, a central time-series database was introduced and made available to all participants. In particular, InfluxDB version 2.7.9 was chosen as it is a free open-source solution, which is widely used and provides enterprise-grade performance.

InfluxDB is well-suited for the project because it has the ability to ingest time-stamped data from manufacturing assets at scale while allowing analytics to be retrieved in an access-flexible way in near real-time or afterward. Organizations registered in the AP are synced with InfluxDB organizations to ensure access control and data sovereignty. Data within InfluxDB is organized in buckets which serve as logical containers with configurable time retention and access policies. Each bucket is owned, controlled and shared by a specific organization, making it easy to separate datasets by organizational boundaries while aligning with analytics purpose and existing workflows. The database infrastructure is deployed on Kubernetes with PersistentVolumeClaims that deliver durability through automated backups based on Velero, supporting recovery from unplanned outages. Fine-grained authorization to access sensor data is enforced through integration with Keycloak to ensure that consortium members have the proper access permissions on their respective asset subscriptions. Multiple protocols are supported for ingesting data into the database, including InfluxDB line protocol for direct connections and REST

API endpoints for higher level applications, accommodating direct sensor connections and batch-oriented data ingestion.

7.2 Time-series Database Integration

The time-series database connects to both the EDC Connector and Authority Portal, allowing data access to be semantically aware and governed by policy. During the asset registration process in the Connector, data providers indicate their InfluxDB buckets and retention policies as a part of the data address configuration specified in D2.2 Section 6.2. If the data has been added to Influx via the Data Vault, the user can select the corresponding Data Vault asset from a dropdown menu. If the data has been added to InfluxDB in another way, the user can provide a JSON snippet containing the InfluxDB bucket, access tokens and other asset-related properties. This enables consumers to query specific time ranges without needing to download entire historical datasets. Upon successful contract negotiation, DAPS provides bucket-level authorization credentials to consumers to access the buckets as contractually agreed upon via ODRL policies. Predictive maintenance services that are containerized and deployed in Kubernetes use the influxdb-client Python library to access the input data at the start of the analysis and store the results back to the specified bucket at the end of the analysis, thus providing an audit trail for all analyses conducted.

The EDC Connector integration layer uses InfluxDB REST endpoints for service-to-service communication with all calls protected by OAuth2 tokens issued by DAPS. A critical integration development turned CORS on for the Elasticsearch instance backing the Authority Portal's metadata indices. The configuration (CORS options: allow-origin, allow-methods, allow-headers; IP whitelisting; TLS encryption) enabled the Authority Portal and Grafana dashboards to access both the Elasticsearch metadata indices and InfluxDB time-series metrics from browser-based interfaces, resulting in joint visibility of operational data flows and exchange activity patterns while remaining compliant with security policies.

The staging environment deployment (the product of the EDC component upgrade testing effort) incorporates a complete InfluxDB instance with the same configuration as production, which facilitates testing data ingestion pipelines and querying performance under more realistic load conditions before going to production. The metadata ingester configuration for staging required INNOV to facilitate collaboration with Ontotext to ensure that the corresponding appropriate fully qualified domain name mappings were provided and that namespace isolation was achieved (staging-dataspace namespace). This required work emphasizes the operational complexity of sustaining two environments for CI testing purposes.

7.3 Ingesting predictive data to Influx

Data ingestion is a systematic pipeline that converts raw data from various sources - CSV files stored in MinIO, REST API endpoints, or even directly from sensor connections - to a time series format and schema definitions. The Data Vault component also offers utilities including a file structure modeller using the CSVW vocabulary to define schemas for CSV files that include column-level descriptions, parsing configurations and data types. After a schema is defined, there are automatic ingestion pipelines that rename (sanitization) column names based on the four-layer architecture and convert data types before mapping incoming records to InfluxDB metrics, tags and fields.

Validated use cases mentioned in the D4.2 report incorporate predictive maintenance model outputs including anomaly scores, failure probability predictions, feature importance arrays and temporal patterns, that have been modelled as time-series measurements alongside raw time-series operational parameters when appropriate, to facilitate temporal correlation analysis. The predictive service integration pattern involves the use of containerized ML services to fetch pre-processed historical data from InfluxDB using Flux queries, perform inference based on dataset batches corresponding to 24-hour operational windows and write the result back to dedicated buckets or database. This architecture is an asynchronous integration pattern that supports both batch processing for model training on historical refinery data from 2017-2020 and more recent data from 2024 with granularities ranging from 1-minute to 5-min and near-real-time scoring for operational alerts when data is available without overwhelming the database layer.

Operational hurdles indicated in D4.2 include an absence of a systematic data ingestion pipeline automation where a SCADA system requires multiple-layered VPN authentication, which is noted as an impediment to a sequential ingestion pipeline. While it is not a limiting factor of being able to execute the use case, it was a signal that integrated patterns for association with legacy industrial control systems must be improved, essentially ensuring secure digital appliance data access and deployment. The ingestion framework provides for applicable constraints with configurable authentication middleware and manual batch ingestion that honors designated network security boundaries, while also enabling acceptable data freshness for predictive analytics.

To address the case of integration with legacy systems the consortium identified and implemented a near real-time data sharing scenario for the refinery use case. The consortium devised a pipeline where new sensory data is uploaded to a data provider's FTP server every hour, it is then automatically appended to past sensory data in a dedicated InfluxDB bucket, a predictive analytics service asset is triggered and generates analysis stored in InfluxDB which is made available to the data provider via the Dashboard. After initial asset registration, the whole process of updating data and prediction results is automated using a script which can serve as a template for future integrations with other legacy systems.

7.4 Effector: Explainable AI for Industrial Predictive Maintenance

The Effector XAI (Explainable AI) system represents a successful implementation of explainable AI in industrial predictive maintenance. The integration within the UNDERPIN Manufacturing Dataspace demonstrates the potential of combining semantic technologies with explainable AI to create transparent, trustworthy industrial AI systems.

The system delivers significant operational value through the identification of critical operational thresholds, efficiency zones and individual equipment behavioral patterns. The asynchronous processing architecture ensures scalability while maintaining real-time operational capabilities and the intuitive user interface enables adoption across diverse stakeholder groups.

The success of this deployment validates the approach of integrating sophisticated XAI techniques into existing industrial workflows, providing a foundation for broader adoption of transparent AI in critical industrial applications. The regional explanation capabilities of Effector prove particularly valuable in revealing equipment-specific behaviors that would remain hidden in traditional global explanation approaches.

This implementation establishes a robust foundation for future enhancements and demonstrates the practical viability of explainable AI as a critical component in next-generation industrial predictive maintenance systems.

7.4.1 Effector on Underpin

The Effector XAI system is integrated into the UNDERPIN Manufacturing Dataspace as a specialized explainability service that enhances the transparency and trustworthiness of predictive maintenance operations. Within this ecosystem, Effector serves as the explanation layer that bridges the gap between complex machine learning predictions and actionable maintenance insights. Effector operates within the Dataspace's federated architecture, which enables multiple stakeholders, wind farm operators, equipment manufacturers and maintenance teams to access standardized XAI insights while maintaining data security and organizational boundaries. By leveraging the predictive maintenance results of the sensor data stored in InfluxDB and MinIO, Effector analyzes and reveals how operational parameters influence equipment health predictions.

This integration is particularly critical for UNDERPIN's wind turbine generator use case UC2.1, where sensitive electrical systems and mechanical components in the nacelle and tower are prone to failures that result in prolonged downtimes and high maintenance costs. The Effector service enhances UNDERPIN's confidence to adopt AI-driven maintenance strategies across the entire manufacturing dataspace ecosystem.

More specifically, Effector provides model-agnostic explanations via Partial Dependence Plots (PDP) and Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) plots. In the wind turbine use case, PDP analysis reveals the average effect of each operational parameter on bearing temperature predictions, while ICE plots expose individual turbine behavioral variations that would be hidden in global averages. The implementation process involves three key steps: first, loading the trained CatBoost model and preprocessed SCADA data; second, generating PDP curves for each feature across its operational range; and third, overlaying ICE curves to visualize prediction heterogeneity across individual turbine instances.

7.4.2 UC2.1 User Interface and Interaction

The UI provides intuitive data selection capabilities from a dropdown menu with two options: "MinIO" and "InfluxDB". The form fields are dynamically shown based on the selected data source.

MinIO: Text field for CSV filename specification

Effector-Xai Analysis

AI-generated plots and analysis from the effector-Xai bucket

 Refresh

Data for XAI
Analyze Data
Results

Data Processing
Process data from MinIO or InfluxDB for XAI analysis

Data Source

MinIO
▼

CSV Filename

▶ Process Data

Figure 3 - UC2.1 User Interface for Data Processing for Effector via MinIO

InfluxDB: Date range pickers and bucket selection interface

Effector-Xai Analysis

AI-generated plots and analysis from the effector-Xai bucket

 Refresh

Data for XAI
Analyze Data
Results

Data Processing
Process data from MinIO or InfluxDB for XAI analysis

Data Source

InfluxDB
▼

Start Time (ISO format) **End Time (ISO format)**

📅

📅

Buckets (comma-separated)

▶ Process Data

Figure 4 - UC2.1 User Interface for Data Processing for Effector via InfluxDB

The data is processed and available to Effector XAI to analyze. Next step is to trigger the analysis of the data from the next tab:

Effector-Xai Analysis

AI-generated plots and analysis from the effector-Xai bucket

 Refresh

Data for XAI
Analyze Data
Results

Generate Analysis Plots
Start XAI analysis to produce plots for selected features

Start Time (ISO format)
01/01/2019 11:37 πμ

End Time (ISO format)
01/04/2020 11:38 πμ

Filename
WF1_WTIG.csv

Features to Analyze

- Generator RPM Max.
- Nacelle Temp. Avg.
- Generator CoolingWater Temp. Avg.
- Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 0 Avg.
- Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 1 Avg.

 Analyze Data / Produce Plots

Figure 5 - Analyze Data Page

We choose the filename and the start and end time of the data we want to produce explainability plots for. The feature selection for analysis comes with a multi-select dropdown with key operational parameters:

- Generator RPM Max
- Nacelle Temperature Average
- Generator Cooling Water Temperature Average
- Production Latest Average Active Power Gen 0/1 Average

If none is selected, then all the features are considered for explainability by default. The process is asynchronous and can take more than an hour to produce all plots. For this reason, a UUID, which is a universally unique identifier (128-bit number), designed to be a unique identifier for the background running jobs is generated, and one can check the status of the processing jobs.

The results of this process become available in the results tab:

Figure 6 - Generator RPM Max vs Generator Bearing Temp. Avg. Effector Result

Figure 7 - Generator RPM Max vs Nacelle Temp. Avg. Effector Result

Figure 8 - Generator CoolingWater Temp. Avg. vs Generator Bearing Temp. Avg. Effector Result

All plots show the relationship between different wind turbine operational features and the Generator Bearing Temperature Average. The red bands represent PDP curves with uncertainty intervals, while the blue line shows ICE (Individual Conditional Expectation) curves.

Figure 6 displays relatively stable bearing temperatures across most RPM ranges (1100-1700 RPM), hovering around 0. However, there's a serious spike at higher RPMs (1800+), where bearing temperature jumps to around +4-5, indicating potential overheating issues at maximum operational speeds.

Figure 7 shows a steady, approximately linear positive relationship. As nacelle temperature increases from 24°C to 36°C, bearing temperature rises from about -2 to +6. This suggests ambient conditions in the nacelle directly influence bearing thermal performance.

Figure 8 shows a strong positive correlation. As cooling water temperature increases from ~29°C to 35°C, the bearing temperature rises sharply from around -5 to +10. There's a notable step-like increase around 30-31°C, suggesting a threshold effect where cooling efficiency may be compromised.

These visualizations help identify which operational parameters most significantly impact bearing temperature, useful for predictive maintenance strategies.

7.4.3 Effector Architecture Overview

The Effector XAI system operates within a Dataspace Environment and follows a modular pipeline architecture with five distinct processing stages:

1. Model Loader

The entry point loads a pre-trained model: a CatBoost classifier for anomaly predictions. This model is used from the predictive analysis application and serves as the foundation for generating predictions.

2. PDP Analysis Module

This component initiates the explanation generation process through plot creation and asynchronous processing, preparing the data for parallel feature analysis.

3. Thread Pool Executor

A critical scalability component that enables parallel feature processing with 2-3 maximum workers. This prevents resource exhaustion while processing multiple features concurrently (Generator RPM Max, Nacelle Temperature, Cooling Water Temperature, Active Power Generation, etc.).

4. PDP Engine

The core XAI computation unit that generates PDP Plots and Individual Conditional Expectation plots, performing the actual feature effect analysis that reveals how each operational parameter influences bearing temperature predictions.

5. Plot Generator

The final stage creates Matplotlib-based visualizations, encoding them in Base64 format and PNG files for storage and retrieval.

7.4.4 Data Flow Architecture

The system reads from two storage sources:

- MinIO: CSV files containing historical wind turbine sensor data
- InfluxDB: Time series database for real-time data retrieval and results storage

Results flow back to InfluxDB, which stores job status, PDP results and metadata, while a monitoring dashboard provides visualization and tracking capabilities.

This architecture achieves a balance between computational efficiency (through parallelization) and system stability (through controlled resource allocation), making it suitable for production deployment in industrial environments.

Figure 9 - Effector Architecture

7.4.5 Effector Interaction Flow and Sequence

Figure 10 - Effector Sequence Diagram

The workflow begins when a user requests PDP/ICE plot generation through the User Interface. The FastAPI Service receives this request and immediately validates it with the Data Preprocessing module, which confirms data availability and parameter correctness before proceeding. The system follows a conditional data retrieval path based on user selection:

- **InfluxDB Path:** When the data source is InfluxDB, the FastAPI Service queries wind turbine manufacturing data using the specified date range (`start_time`, `end_time`) and bucket parameters. InfluxDB returns time series sensor measurements directly to the service.
- **MinIO Path:** Alternatively, when MinIO is selected, the service retrieves CSV files containing historical wind turbine data using the specified filename parameter. MinIO returns the raw manufacturing data files.

This dual-path architecture provides flexibility for different data access patterns -real-time queries from InfluxDB or batch processing from MinIO archives.

Once data is acquired, the FastAPI Service delegates the explanation generation to the Effector Library, requesting "Process data and generate explanations (PDP/ICE)". The Effector Library performs the computationally intensive work of generating PDPs and ICE plots with regional explanations, revealing both global feature effects and individual turbine behavioral variations. After analysis completion, the system stores results in InfluxDB. The FastAPI Service sends the plot data to InfluxDB in order to save them, in base64-encoded format, along with comprehensive metadata (feature names, timestamps, job identifiers) ensuring reproducibility and audit trail capabilities. Then, from the User Interface, the user can fetch generated plots and explanations through multiple pathways. The User Interface first receives notification that plots and explanations are ready. Subsequently, it can fetch the complete results from InfluxDB, which returns the stored plots and explanations. Finally, the User Interface visualizes the PDP/ICE plots and regional explanations, enabling maintenance engineers to interpret model behavior and make informed operational decisions.

Some key architectural decisions are:

1. **Asynchronous Processing:** The separation between request initiation and result retrieval enables non-blocking operations for long-running analyses.
2. **Dual Storage Strategy:** InfluxDB serves both as a data source (time series queries) and results repository (plot storage), while MinIO provides archival storage for raw CSV files.
3. **Service Orchestration:** The FastAPI Service acts as the central orchestrator, coordinating between data sources, processing libraries and storage layers.
4. **Stateful Tracking:** The notification mechanism enables progress monitoring and supports the UUID-based job tracking system described in the architecture.

7.4.6 Core Components

The Effector XAI system comprises several interconnected components:

- **Backend Service:** FastAPI-based REST service handling XAI analysis requests
- **Data Storage Layer:** Integration with InfluxDB for time series data and MinIO for object storage

- Analysis Engine: Effector library providing PDP/ICE plot generation with regional explanations
- Visualization Layer: Matplotlib-based plot generation with base64 encoding
- User Interface: Web-based dashboard for interactive model exploration

7.4.7 Technology Stack

- Backend Framework: FastAPI (Python)
- XAI Library: Effector (custom Python package for tabular data explanations)
- Machine Learning: CatBoost classifier for anomaly detection
- Data Storage: InfluxDB (time series), MinIO (object storage)
- Visualization: Matplotlib, integrated dashboard interface
- Concurrency: ThreadPoolExecutor for parallel processing
- Authentication: Integrated with Manufacturing Dataspace security

XAI Analysis EngineThe core XAI functionality leverages the Effector library's advanced capabilities for global explanations using Partial Dependence Plots (PDP), showing average feature effects across operational ranges. These PDP plots can reveal fleet-wide behavioral patterns and optimal operating zones. One can also produce regional explanations using Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) plots exposing individual equipment variations. The ICE automatic detects subspaces for reduced heterogeneity and identifies equipment-specific behavioral patterns. Key features are model-agnostic approach supporting CatBoost and other ML frameworks, heterogeneity-aware ALE (RHALE) implementation and sophisticated algorithms for automatic subspace detection.

8. Metadata Management

In the context of the UNDERPIN Data Space, metadata management involves collecting, enriching, semantically organizing and discovering information that describes datasets, their provenance, quality attributes and contexts for use. Unlike other dataspace, UNDERPIN allows the use of detailed heterogeneous schemas for asset metadata, enabling richer description and facilitating discoverability.

To facilitate this, the metadata infrastructure brings together GraphDB for metadata storage, ElasticSearch index and KnowDS for semantic searching capabilities and the Vocabulary Hub to establish a common discovery and interoperability framework as outlined in D2.2 Section 6.2. This section takes a simple case from both refineries and wind farms where disparate manufacturing data have been harmonized through the use of standardized ontologies and vocabularies, allowing all participants to discover assets semantically with the ability to exchange data with semantic transparency.

8.1 Metadata Ingestor: Creation, Integration and Deployment

The Metadata Ingestor Service automatically fills the metadata repository (GraphDB) with descriptions of the asset and semantic metadata from the Data Vault configurations, EDC Connector registrations and information provided by participants. In order to receive this data, the ingestor is deployed alongside a Catalog Crawler – a basic Connector which queries the AP for available connectors and then queries each of them to collect their data asset catalogs.

The Metadata Ingestor Service periodically collects asset descriptions, addresses of data (S3 paths, InfluxDB buckets, REST endpoints), policy constraints and structural information about the asset. For assets associated with files that adhere to the CSV format, the ingestor extracts schema definitions that have been captured using the CSVW vocabulary according to the Data Vault file structure modeller, which collects column-level descriptions, data types, parsing configurations and semantic mappings. The ingestor takes heterogeneous representations of the asset and converts them into RDF-based metadata that adheres to the IDS Information Model and DCAT vocabulary extensions, which enables harmonization across multiple data providers and protocol adapters.

Integration with Keycloak ensures that only authorized ingestor instances can access sensitive asset metadata, with coordinated per-group and per-bucket granularity. The ingestor offers configurable synchronization intervals (usually 5-15 minutes) to balance the freshness of metadata with the load on the cluster. Their retry logic for transient ingestion failures after a metadata source is down is also configurable. A critical operational decision was that each Catalog Crawler instance requires its own Metadata Ingestor—not a centralized, shared ingestor—to prevent conflict configuration entries when concurrently operating the crawlers within staging and production. This one-ingestor-per-crawler pattern avoids cross-contamination of metadata ingestor queues from concurrent processing of heterogeneous data sources and resolves the issue of scheduling conflicting ingestors on Extracted Data Sources.

The deployment uses a Helm-based model with ingestor configuration separated into values.yaml (shared settings, such as broker endpoints) and mounted ConfigMaps (connector-specific configurations) with values securely stored in Vault. PersistentVolumeClaims in backing Elasticsearch indices provide the persistence of metadata indices (and settings) through pod restarts and upgrades. The workflow is monitored and benchmarked via Prometheus, capturing ingestion rate, error count, latency percentiles and with alerting rules when ingestion lag exceeds configurable settings (typical alert on >30 minute lag).

8.2 Deployment of the Metadata Storage (GraphDB)

The metadata describing an asset in a typical dataspace is limited to a set of predetermined features which are relevant to most assets in the dataspace, such as data type, time period and other asset-level descriptors. UNDERPIN overcomes this limitation by using a triplestore (GraphDB) to store metadata in RDF format. This allows for different assets to be described using different features at a more detailed level, such as column-descriptors for time-series or tabular assets. In this way a data asset about wind turbine sensory readings can describe that the drivetrain acceleration reading in a particular column is measured in revolutions per second, while an asset about a refinery can describe that the bearing temperature of a steam turbine is measured in Celsius.

To ensure interoperability, the set of measurement units, quantity kinds and components are controlled via the Vocabulary Hub described later in this document. Schemas describing in detail the unit, quantity kind and component of each column can be created, modified and re-used via the Data Vault, also described later in this document.

The Metadata Storage. a central GraphDB instance, contains metadata stored in the RDF-based metadata format and is compliant with IDS standards. A GraphDB Elasticsearch Connector provides faceted and full-text search indexing for quick discovery queries directly from the Authority Portal front-end. The system utilizes both query expressiveness when searching across

GraphDB with SPARQL and search performance when utilized in the Elasticsearch where it utilizes Lucene-based ranking.

Whenever the metadata of any asset in the dataspace has changed (modified, retained, deleted), it takes only seconds for the Metadata Ingestor Service to propagate this information to GraphDB and the Elasticsearch index.

The Metadata Storage deployment includes horizontal pod autoscaling (HPA), targeting CPU consumption at 70%, to assure the level of query performance remains responsive as participant user numbers and asset counts increase. Other configuration options include graph query timeouts (10-30 seconds) to prevent resource depletion from larger SPARQL complexity and paginating results to avoid memory exhaustion on large/complex metadata SPARQL queries.

8.3 KnowDS: Using Metadata for Supporting Semantic Search

KnowDS is a system that is integrated into the UNDERPIN Dataspace (DS) and provides advanced semantic search capabilities. KnowDS represents a significant enhancement to traditional data asset discovery mechanisms by leveraging the descriptive metadata of the data assets to enable intelligent discovery through the use of ontologies, knowledge graphs and Steiner trees.

8.3.1 KnowDS Overview

KnowDS addresses critical limitations in current Data Space implementations by enabling semantic search capabilities beyond simple keyword filtering.

The data consumer may enter freely any set of query terms or select from a list of suggested keywords. As a first step, KnowDS uses a domain ontology to allow the expansion of the query with other terms used in the Dataspace, either more specific or more general ones. Moreover, KnowDS constructs a relevance graph connecting the data assets of the Dataspace. The second step is to use this relevance graph and the query set in order to construct a Steiner tree containing the results. In this way, the results may contain data assets that do not explicitly contain any of the query terms but are still relevant to the query.

This process is explained in detail in what follows.

Data Synchronization

KnowDS uses the asset metadata stored in the UNDERPIN DS in order to implement its search method. UNDERPIN DS keeps those metadata in a GraphDB database, while KnowDS uses Apache Solr as its data repository. To keep in sync with the UNDERPIN DS asset metadata, KnowDS is notified about any change to the metadata and updates its own data repository and internal structures to reflect this change. To this end, KnowDS uses a module called Synchronization Engine that regularly monitors the UNDERPIN GraphDB for changes and notifies KnowDS.

Semantic Graph Creation

Each data asset in a Dataspace is associated with descriptive metadata consisting of simple fields. KnowDS uses only a few of those fields, namely the title, the tags and the description. The title and description are self-explanatory. The tags field is a set of keywords related to the data asset. We assume that the tags have a semantic orientation and refer to the concepts that

characterize the data asset. Finally, a couple of identifiers are used: the connector endpoint identifies the connector of the data provider and the asset ID identifies the data asset itself. Those two identifiers allow the data consumer to start a negotiation for the specific data asset with the data provider, through their respective connectors.

Figure 11 - KnowDS User Interface showing the query expansion feature for the term “rotor”

KnowDS uses the tags fields to build a relevance graph connecting data assets.

- Each node in the relevance graph represents a data asset. An edge between two nodes represents the tags that the nodes have in common and the label of the edge is the common tags separated by commas.
- Each edge has a number attached, indicating the number of common tags that the edge represents. This number is called relevance strength and denotes the relevance between the nodes connected by the edge. The more common keywords between two assets, the

higher the relevance strength between them. Obviously, if two nodes do not share any tag, they are not connected by an edge.

Query Expansion

The user (the data consumer, in DS terms) starts by freely inserting a set of terms in the query box. Alternatively, they may select terms from the list of keywords already used for describing the data assets. For each term, a pop-up window displays relevant terms (according to the domain ontology), which are either more general, more specific, or similar (see Figure 12). Each displayed term is accompanied by a number indicating the number of data assets that would be returned. The user may select any of the displayed terms and include them in the query.

Data Asset Matching

To find a data asset, the data consumer provides KnowDS with a set of query terms. KnowDS aims to find the relevant data assets in the DS and rank them according to their semantic proximity to the terms, using the relevance graph. The task proceeds in three steps:

- First, we find the set of nodes in the relevance graph that contain one or more of the provided terms in their tags, title, or description. We call this set the set of direct results.
- Then, we construct the Steiner tree that contains all the nodes in the direct results set. The Steiner tree is the least-cost connected subgraph of the relevance graph that contains these nodes. We set the cost between two nodes connected by an edge with relevance strength N to be $1 / N$. Intuitively, a node that connects two or more of the nodes in the direct result set will be part of the Steiner tree, even if this node is not part of the direct result set (see Figure 13). The result of the query will consist of all the nodes of the Steiner tree and will include the direct result set plus the nodes that act as in-betweens. This way, the results may contain nodes that are indeed relevant, but do not contain any of the initial terms. When constructing the Steiner tree, we also consider the case that the relevance graph is a disconnected graph.
- Finally, we rank the results. The nodes of the Steiner tree are ranked by combining two score components. The first score is the text relevance score, which reflects how well the textual content of each node matches the query terms. This score captures the fact that nodes containing more search terms are more relevant. The second score is the connectivity score that captures the importance of each node within the Steiner tree. This score is calculated as the sum of the relevance strength of all edges of the node. Higher connectivity score means that the node exhibits stronger connections with its neighbours, constituting a more central node that bridges many related nodes. The final ranking score for each node, called combined relevance score, is then computed by multiplying the (normalized) text relevance score by the (normalized) connectivity score. Therefore, a node must have both a high textual relevance score and a high connectivity score to be ranked high.

Figure 12 - A Steiner tree, introducing a new node (green color) in the results

The result of the query is the nodes of the Steiner tree, ranked according to the combined relevance score explained above.

8.3.2 Software Components

KnowDS uses the following key components:

Data Layer

- Apache Solr: Primary data repository for KnowDS internal structures and metadata.
- Relevance Graph Storage: Graph-based data structure for semantic relationships.

Integration Layer

- Metadata Sync Service: A Spring boot application that reads metadata from the GraphDB, transforms them and sends them to KnowDS.
- Synchronization Engine: Maintains consistency between DS metadata and KnowDS repository.

Processing Layer

- Query expansion module: Handles the expansion with relevant terms, by making use of the domain ontology.
- Semantic Graph Builder: Constructs relevance graphs from asset tags.
- Steiner Tree Calculator: Identifies optimal connected subgraphs for query results.
- Ranking Engine: Combines text relevance and connectivity scores.

Presentation Layer

- KnowDS Web Interface: User-facing search and discovery portal.
- API Gateway: RESTful interface for programmatic access.

8.3.3 User Interface and Interaction

Search Terms

The user may enter search terms in the autocomplete field. They can use the drop-down feature for suggestions of terms already used in the DataSpace, or type their own search term. They can add multiple terms by pressing Enter or Tab after each term. By clicking the gear icon that is next to any term, the user can explore concept expansions and related terms from the knowledge base.

Term Expansion

When the user clicks the gear icon on a search term, they will see suggestions for broader concepts, variant terms and narrower concepts. The user can then select checkboxes to include these related terms in the search, expanding their query to find more relevant results that might have been missed.

Semantic Graph Matching

Results are identified by matching the query terms (including any expansions) against a similarity graph that connects all the assets of the Data Space. The use of a Steiner tree ensures that relevant connecting assets are returned even if they don't directly match any of the query terms.

UI Features

- **Search:** Executes the query with the selected terms and any expansions that have been chosen.
- **View ontology graph:** Visualizes the knowledge base taxonomy structure showing concepts and their relationships, with the option to download the taxonomy as an RDF/XML file from the graph viewer.
- **View similarity graph:** Visualizes the relationships between all items in the dataset.
- **View Steiner graph:** Shows the connecting paths between the search results.

Understanding Results

Search results are ranked using a combination of text relevance and graph-based similarity. Items that are introduced by Steiner trees as connecting elements that bridge search terms, are highlighted and labelled accordingly (see Figure 13 - The ranked list of results and the detailed card of the selected data asset).

Figure 13 - The ranked list of results and the detailed card of the selected data asset

8.3.4 KnowDS Metadata and Ontology

KnowDS Asset Metadata

The asset metadata catalog of the UNDERPIN dataspace consists of entries that almost exclusively fall into two dataset categories: Wind Farm/Turbine data and Refinery Compressor data. Each category comprises data assets published by a single dataspace participant. Additionally, all data assets within each category share identical or nearly identical controlled-vocabulary field values with exhaustive detail and completeness. Finally, published data assets lack descriptive free text.

As a consequence, the asset metadata catalog exhibits minimal diversity (two data asset providers corresponding to two distinct data asset classes, with near-complete homogeneity across assets within each class). This differs from production scenarios, where multiple participants publish data asset offers displaying varying degrees of data quality and completeness. In real-world scenarios, metadata descriptions also range from comprehensive

and detailed to sparse or absent, reflecting heterogeneous contributions from dataspace participants.

To mitigate this unrealistic uniformity and demonstrate KnowDS usage under conditions more closely approximating production, the following modification steps were taken:

- **Field value dropping:** We reduced field values for metadata items by dropping up to 80% of field values, primarily targeting the "features" field (corresponding to dataset columns). Related values from correlated fields (quantities, qualifiers, units) were removed for consistency. This creates realistic gaps in data/metadata coverage, mirroring production scenarios in two ways: first, some data assets contain fewer measured features/columns and second, metadata documentation may be lacking, even when the underlying dataset is comprehensive.
- **Non-empty and diverse textual descriptions:** We created metadata descriptions of varying length (200-400 words), based on actual field values and aligned with the UNDERPIN domain ontology. Some descriptions are comprehensive, employing domain-specific terminology, while others are sparse or incomplete, reflecting realistic variability in data documentation quality.

These modifications produce metadata items approximating production dataspace scenarios where diversity in data coverage and data documentation quality is expected. Using the constructed metadata items, two key aspects of KnowDS search can be demonstrated: query term expansion (expanding searches with additional terms using underlying term semantic relations) and query resultset expansion using Steiner points (discovering connecting items that bridge assets in query resultsets, even if connecting items don't directly match query terms).

KnowDS Domain Ontology

KnowDS employs a custom domain ontology, henceforth referred to as the "KnowDS ontology", for query term expansion. The KnowDS ontology is supplied by the KnowDS administrator and is maintained by a domain expert. We adopted the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) to model the domain knowledge constituting the KnowDS ontology. We focus on concept labels (both preferred and alternative labels, capturing synonyms and variants) and broader/narrower hierarchical relations between concepts.

Concepts may be optionally organized into concept schemes for thematic grouping. While the full expressive power of SKOS may be utilized, not all elements are currently employed for query term expansion (for instance, "related" relations are currently ignored during search expansion).

For the KnowDS ontology used in the UNDERPIN KnowDS deployment, the comprehensive UNDERPIN ontology served as the foundation but was simplified to focus on search-relevant elements. Synonyms were employed as alternative labels within concepts to enable query expansion with term variants and broader/narrower relations were introduced between concepts to enable hierarchical query expansion. When the KnowDS ontology changes through addition of new concepts, refinement of concept relations, or incorporation of new terminology, the KnowDS administrator may submit the updated SKOS file to immediately drive query term expansion, ensuring the KnowDS search system remains aligned with evolving domain knowledge.

9. Data Storage

9.1 Overview

Data spaces are primarily used to facilitate data exchange between participants, under the principles of sovereignty and trust. The Connector components of a Data space are not meant to store any data, but rather used as gateways to where the data is stored. Thus, Connectors provide mechanisms for accessing the actual data source through a variety of protocols such as HTTP REST, S3 or SQL. However, in some cases a simpler approach is preferred as per technical or business policy restrictions.

To this end, the UNDERPIN Data Space offers a service called the Data Vault. The main role of the Data Vault is to provide participants a data storage facility where they can simply upload files, which can be then provided as assets on the Data space, through each participant’s Connector. The Data Vault provides a set of utilities that can aid participants to provide their data on the Data Space:

- File Storage on an S3 provider
- File Structure Modeller, to define the schema of a CSV file using the CSVW vocabulary
- Automatic ingestion to a Timeseries database, based on the user defined CSV schema
- Integration with the participants Connector during asset registration to auto-fill Data Address specification of the asset description

Figure 14 - High Level Architecture of the Data Space

9.2 Data and Metadata flows

In Figure 14 the high level architecture of the UNDERPIN Data Space is shown. The Data Vault communicates with several of the main components:

- The Authority’s Portal Keycloak (not shown in diagram) is used as an Identity provider. Groups registered on the Authority Portal have access to the Data Vault using the same

credentials. Members of the same group have access to the assets of the group, i.e., being able to upload or modify files, create a schema or ingest some datasets on the Timeseries Database.

- The Data Vault uses the S3 File Storage server, in this case an instance of MinIO deployed on the cluster, as file storage. All files uploaded on the Data Vault are directly stored in MinIO. Each group of the Authority Portal has a dedicated bucket in MinIO. The Data Vault is responsible of creating and managing relevant access keys for each object.
- The Vault, an instance of Hashicorp Vault, is used to store the access keys associated with each file provided by the Data Vault. Each key provides read-only access to a specific file object, which is then used as part of the Asset Data Address Configuration, during asset registration on the connector.
- The GraphDB instance is used to store basic file metadata and the Structure Definition of a CSV file, in case this is provided.
- The Structure Definition can be modelled using the Modeller UI component of the Data Vault (Figure 18). Through this, the user can provide a description of the structure of the CSV file object, such as parsing configuration or detailed description of each column of the CSV file object. We are using the CSVW vocabulary to describe the structure of the CSVs. The model and the forms can be dynamically extended by specifying the additional properties using SHACL.

Structure Definition Titles

Provide one or more titles for the structure definition, specifying languages for each.

Refinery Schema

@en

Rt

Add Title

Dialect Properties

Define how the file's content should be interpreted by specifying the dialect's configuration.

Encoding ?

utf-8

Delimiter ?

.

Quote Character ?

"

Skip Rows ?

0

Comment Prefix ?

#

Header Row Count ?

1

Skip Columns ?

0

Trim ?

None

Skip Blank Rows Double Quote Header Skip Initial Space

Structure Definition

```

"modified": 1738068216427,
"created": 1714521600000,
"dialect": {
  "uri": "https://datavault.underpin.eu/",
  "id": "9fa4cd95-9a74-4aec-bb7f-74314fc",
  "types": [],
  "properties": {},
  "encoding": "utf-8",
  "quoteChar": "\"",
  "doubleQuote": true,
  "skipRows": 0,
  "commentPrefix": "#",
  "header": true,
  "headerRowCount": 1,
  "delimiter": ",",
  "skipColumns": 0,
  "skipBlankRows": true,
  "skipInitialSpace": false,
  "trim": "true"
},
"tableSchema": {
  "uri": "https://datavault.underpin.eu/",
  "id": "71563fa4-5818-4ce4-8214-ad63988",
  "types": [],
  "properties": {},
  "columns": [
    {
      "uri": "https://datavault.underpin.eu/",
      "id": "a6fb4125-7fc6-4d63-8100-bf",
      "types": [],
      "properties": {},
      "name": "75PI808.pv",
      "titles": [
        {
          "value": "p",
          "language": "en"
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "description": "p",
    
```

Cancel Next

Figure 15 - Data Vault Modeller UI for Structure Definition

- The Timeseries database, an InfluxDB instance, is used to store data in the form of timeseries. As per requirements described in D2.2, for a set of use cases it is useful to provide data in the form of timeseries where consumers are able to have access to specific parts of the database without having to download the whole dataset, using a query language. Data Vault automates this procedure by utilizing the user defined Structure definition of CSV files. The ingestion to InfluxDB is then driven by the Structure definition, handling any transformations needed based on the schema. In addition, data from heterogeneous sources could be integrated into a single timeseries, given that the provided Structure definition maps to the same properties.

10. Operational Upkeep and Monitoring

10.1 Ensuring components availability

The UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure implements comprehensive availability mechanisms to maintain operational excellence and meet the high availability requirements specified in D2.2. Component availability is ensured through multiple layers of redundancy and automated health monitoring as documented in D3.1.

All critical components are deployed with multi-replica configurations across availability zones. The Kubernetes cluster spans multiple zones on Hetzner infrastructure, ensuring resilience against single-zone failures. Key components maintain the following availability profiles:

- EDC Connectors: replicas with horizontal pod autoscaling
- Authority Portal: Minimum 2 replicas with load balancing
- DAPS (Keycloak): High availability mode with database clustering
- InfluxDB: Clustered deployment with data replication
- Metadata Broker: Redundant instances with shared PostgreSQL backend

Automated Health Checks: Each microservice exposes health endpoints that are monitored by Kubernetes liveness and readiness probes. Services failing health checks are automatically restarted or removed from load balancer rotation.

Resource Management: Components are configured with appropriate resource requests and limits per D3.1 specifications:

- CPU: 1-4 cores per service based on workload characteristics
- Memory: 2-8GB RAM allocation with automatic scaling triggers
- Storage: Persistent volumes with automated backup and recovery

Failover Mechanisms: Database connections include automatic failover configurations and stateless services can be rapidly replaced without data loss. The blockchain node maintains consensus through the distributed ledger architecture.

10.2 Alerts system creation based on K8s components errors

A comprehensive alerting system has been implemented to proactively detect and respond to infrastructure issues, fulfilling the monitoring requirements outlined in D2.2 Section 12.

Prometheus-Based Monitoring: The monitoring stack is built on Prometheus for metrics collection, with custom alert rules configured for UNDERPIN-specific scenarios:

- Pod restart frequency exceeding thresholds
- Memory and CPU utilization beyond 80% sustained usage
- Persistent volume capacity approaching limits
- Network connectivity failures between services
- Certificate expiration warnings (30-day and 7-day alerts)

Grafana Dashboard Integration: Real-time dashboards provide visual monitoring of system health with the following key metrics:

- Component availability status across all services
- Data transfer volumes and success rates
- Authentication and authorization failure rates
- Database connection pool utilization
- API response times and error rates

Multi-Channel Alerting: Alerts are delivered through multiple channels to ensure rapid response:

- Email notifications for critical infrastructure failures
- Slack integration for team collaboration on issues
- PagerDuty escalation for out-of-hours critical alerts
- SMS notifications for datacenter-level outages

Alert Rule Configuration (examples from implementation):

- alert: UnderpinServiceDown

expr: up{job="underpin-components"} == 0

for: 5m

labels:

severity: critical

annotations:

summary: "UNDERPIN service {{ \$labels.instance }} is down"

- alert: HighMemoryUsage

```
expr: (node_memory_MemTotal_bytes - node_memory_MemAvailable_bytes) / node_memory_MemTotal_bytes > 0.8
```

for: 10m

labels:

severity: warning

annotations:

summary: "High memory usage on {{ \$labels.instance }}"

Uptime Kuma Integration: The Authority Portal integrates with Uptime Kuma for external monitoring of critical endpoints, providing status information via API metrics as documented in D3.1. This includes monitoring of:

- DAPS token endpoint availability
- Catalog Crawler search functionality
- EDC connector protocol endpoints
- Blockchain node RPC (Remote Procedure Call) interfaces

Log Aggregation and Analysis: Centralized logging through the ELK stack (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana) enables:

- Structured log analysis across all components
- Automated anomaly detection in application logs
- Security event correlation and alerting
- Performance trend analysis and capacity planning

Incident Response Automation: Critical alerts trigger automated response workflows:

- Automatic service restarts for transient failures
- Traffic rerouting during component maintenance
- Backup restoration procedures for data corruption events
- Scaling adjustments based on load patterns

11. Vocabulary Hub

11.1 What is the Vocabulary Hub

Interoperability in the IDS requires standardized, shared vocabularies to describe data, services and contracts. These vocabularies - lists of controlled, standardized terms - must be machine-readable and support lookups for new terms. The IDS RAM uses RDF for encoding data and its Information Model serves as the core vocabulary shared by all participants.

However, since this core model only covers the minimum common terms, domain-specific applications often need extended vocabularies. These extensions are managed and published through the IDS Vocabulary Hub, a Data Space component that hosts, maintains, documents and versions vocabularies while providing IDS-conform interfaces for seamless communication with IDS components.

There is no known publicly available implementation of a Vocabulary Hub component for the EDC based Data Spaces. To this end, the UNDERPIN project developed and deployed a prototype EDC compliant Vocabulary Hub component with the main goal of being the single source of truth for resolving URI (Uniform Resource Identifier) resources and maintaining use case specific vocabularies across the UNDERPIN Data Space.

11.2 Vocabulary Hub Modules

The Vocabulary Hub component is based on the architecture of the EDC framework. It is composed of several extension components, each one of which offers a specific functionality. The modules that were developed are summarized in the following:

- **vocabulary-hub-spi:** This component is the only non-EDC service extension on the stack. It provides the shared interfaces needed by the other components, like the ResourceDescriptionResolver Interface, or the Resource model. Extensions can provide implementations of the interfaces and register them on the registry of an instance, making it available for other components.
- **vocabulary-hub-controlplane:** This module is a Service Extension, which provides the needed controllers on the control plane of an EDC based connector. To resolve a URI on a vocabulary Hub, a user of a connector needs to send a ResourceDescriptionRequest through the control plane of his own EDC-Connector. The controller is responsible of receiving the resource description requests from the users of the connector and dispatch the request through the Data Space protocol message dispatcher to the specified Vocabulary Hub. The response of the request is a description of the resource in JSON-LD. This component is the only one needed to be added on any connector that needs to use the Vocabulary Hub.
- **inmemory-vault-initializer:** This module is a Service Extension providing an inmemory-vault implementation. It is used by the vocabulary-hub-launcher module to configure the certificate and private key needed to authenticate the Vocabulary Hub connector through the DAPS.
- **vocabulary-hub-protocol:** This module is a Service Extension providing the controller and relevant transformers for the handling of the DSP (Dataspace Protocol) relevant messages, like the ResourceDescriptionRequestMessage. The controller is deployed on the protocol context of the Vocabulary Hub connector and it is the one receiving the DSP relevant messages. This module is only used on the Vocabulary Hub connector or to any other connector on the Data Space that would have a role of a Vocabulary Hub.
- **vocabulary-hub-graphdb:** This module is a Service Extension, which provides a ResourceDescriptionResolver implementation based on GraphDB. This module configures a GraphDB client based on specific environment variables which is used by the resolver implementation.
- **vocabulary-hub-launcher:** This module is the connector launcher. It provides a runtime, configured with all the necessary EDC modules to create an EDC connector with the role of the Vocabulary Hub. The module can be used as a template to create alternative

versions of the connector in case needed, such as in case a different resolver implementation is needed or a different than DAPS identity provider is used on the Data Space.

The external dependencies of the Vocabulary Hub are the Identity Provider, in the case of the UNDERPIN Data Space this is the Keycloak based DAPS implementation and the GraphDB instance, where the descriptions of resources are stored.

11.3 Beyond Resolving Resources

Other than being able to resolve resources on the Data Space, there is the need of creating and maintaining vocabularies. To this end, the consortium decided for a shallow integration of the PoolParty Thesaurus Manager with the Vocabulary Hub in order to allow authorities to create, update and publish vocabularies with the Data Space.

PoolParty does not interact directly with the Vocabulary Hub at this stage, but it stores the vocabularies on the same repository which the Vocabulary Hub uses to resolve the requested resources. This ensures that the resolver always has access to the latest version of the description of a resource.

Therefore, the Vocabulary Hub can be used with or without the presence of a Vocabulary Management tool such as PoolParty and moreover without a dependency on a specific vendor. However, it is recommended to use such a tool in case there are lots of Vocabularies that need to be managed or additional services are needed.

12. Dry-run testing

12.1 Testing Objectives and Scope

This section reports on the activities of task T3.5 “Dry-run testing and operational readiness”. It involves systematically going through the software logic and flow without executing the code in an actual environment. Dry run testing simulates the execution step by step, checking the software’s behavior based on predefined conditions or inputs. The primary goal of dry run testing is to find logical errors, flaws in business logic, or inconsistencies early in the development cycle, helping to address issues before they escalate into more significant problems.

12.2 Testing Methodology and Approach

Dry-run testing was designed to achieve comprehensive validation of dataspace functionality through systematic testing of core components, ensuring robust interoperability between participants and components before and during production deployment. The testing validates critical security measures, data transfer protocols and participant interactions while testing the overall readiness of Dataspace against real-world usage scenarios. All test cases have been developed and implemented in accordance with IDSA/GAIA-X standards and guidelines, ensuring that the testbed functionality meets industry requirements for secure, interoperable Data Spaces. This compliance-first approach guarantees that baseline KPIs and security aspects are achieved before production use-case deployment.

The testing approach follows a structured methodology that maintains an accessible list of test descriptions available to all project partners. The framework incorporates regular discussions and updates to the test suite as new functionality is developed, ensuring comprehensive coverage of evolving system capabilities.

Figure 16 - Cycle process for Dry Run Testing

As Figure 16 - Cycle process for Dry Run Testing shows, the testing process was operated through an iterative cycle where new dataspace features were developed, new tests were incorporated as the new features were added and test coverage was expanded based on partner feedback. The testing list was accessible to all partners during the project lifetime to check. Each test was marked as successful upon completion, or feedback was provided to the relevant modules for remediation and retesting. The systematic execution began in January 2025 and continued until the project completion. This approach ensures that testing activities align with development milestones and component availability.

13. Concluding remarks

This document showcases the final state of the UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure as of November 2025, providing the operational framework for the project's future validation activities and ongoing development. The successful integration and deployment of the full complement of planned components - Authority Portal for participant engagement, DAPS for federated identity management, EDC Connectors for policy-driven exchange of data, blockchain-backed logging for immutable audit trails, time-series storage in InfluxDB for analytics, implementation of semantic metadata systems through the Vocabulary Hub and Catalog Crawler and full operational monitoring infrastructure - demonstrated the technical feasibility of a multi-stakeholder Data Space aligned to IDSA standards and European governance structures.

The deployment activities undertaken during months 12-24 furnish a number of significant technical realities to consider for Data Space futures. Technology maturity of third-party components entailed practical workarounds—custom JSON-LD translation layers for semantic interoperability, automated scripts for UI branding restoration after upgrades, phased staging-based upgrades—that while effective, reinforce the criticality of vendor engagement and component version roadmaps.

The architectural decisions presented in this deliverable embody the lessons learned during the deployment period and enshrine the operational best-practices of the UNDERPIN consortium. The one metadata ingester per crawler pattern alleviates configuration collisions among parallel ingestion streams; diverging storage solutions in the Catalog Crawler (GraphDB for semantic queries and Elasticsearch for full-text search) facilitate optimal query performance based on operational access patterns; and dedicated monitoring strategies with multi-channel alerts provide operational visibility into health metrics for the system. These patterns ensure that a stable, maintainable infrastructure baseline is in place.

The integration test suite (TC-01 through TC-33, Appendix C) executed under Task 3.5 validates functional compliance among all major infrastructure components from authentication and authorization through data transfer workflows, to contract management and blockchain event logging capabilities. The operational readiness validation ensures that the deployed infrastructure meets the availability, responsiveness and observability thresholds established for production-grade applications.

In the future, active management and continual optimization is required of the UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure. Ongoing activities involve maintaining relationships with data vendors for coordinated component upgrades; monitoring system performance and cost optimization as participant numbers increase; and reviewing and evaluating potential emerging standards and technologies to facilitate future incorporation. The infrastructure generated in D3.2 provides the stable and secure basis that is required for the ongoing work towards and for the wider European Data Space community to take learnings from UNDERPIN and the deployment and operation of complex multi-stakeholder data ecosystem.

Appendix A – EDC Deployment Units Configuration

Table 1 - EDC Deployment Units

Deployment Unit	Helm Version	Chart	Replicas	Resource Requests / Limits	Node Selector	Tolerations	Secrets & ConfigMaps
edc-control-plane	edc-ce-1.4.2		2	CPU: 1 core / 2 cores Mem: 2 GB / 4 GB	role: control-plane	- key: "node-role"; value: "worker"; effect: NoSchedule	- edc-control-plane-secret - edc-policies-cm
edc-data-plane	edc-ce-1.4.2		HPA 2-5	CPU: 500 m / 1 core	role: data-plane	- key: "dedicated"; value: "edc";	- edc-data-plane-secret

			Mem: 1 GB / 2 GB		effect: NoExecute	
edc-ui	edc-ui-0.9.1	2	CPU: 200 m / 500 m Mem: 512 MB / 1 GB	role: frontend	- key: "node-role"; value: "frontend"; effect: NoSchedule	- edc-ui-config - oauth-proxy-secret
edc-auth-proxy	edc-auth-connector	1	CPU: 100 m / 200 m Mem: 256 MB / 512 MB	role: frontend	- key: "node-role"; value: "frontend"; effect: NoSchedule	- proxy-tls-secret
edc-postgresql	bitnami/postgresql	1	CPU: 500 m / 1 core Mem: 1 GB / 2 GB	role: database	- key: "storage"; value: "edc-db"; effect: NoSchedule	- postgresql-credentials - pg-initdb-scripts

Notes:

- All EDC units mount Vault Agent sidecars to fetch dynamic secrets at runtime.
- Horizontal Pod Autoscaler (HPA) for edc-data-plane triggers scaling on CPU > 70% and custom queue-length metrics.
- Helm values include nodeSelectors, tolerations and resource specs as shown.
- Secrets are provisioned via Kubernetes Secrets and updated through GitOps pipelines.

Appendix B – AP Deployment Units Configuration

Table 2 - AP Deployment units

Deployment Unit	Helm Chart Version	Replicas	Resource Requests / Limits	Node Selector	Tolerations	Secrets & ConfigMaps
ap-frontend	underpin-ap-1.2.0	2	CPU: 200 m / 500 m Mem: 512 MB / 1 GB	role: frontend	node-role=frontend:NoSchedule	- ap-frontend-config - ingress-tls-secret
ap-backend	underpin-ap-1.2.0	2	CPU: 500 m / 1 core Mem: 1 GB / 2 GB	role: backend	node-role=worker:NoSchedule	- ap-backend-secret - edc-endpoints-cm

catalog-crawler	underpin-mb-0.8.3	HPA 1-3	CPU: 250 m / 500 m Mem: 512 MB / 1 GB	role: data-plane	dedicated=metadata:NoExecute	- mb-db-credentials - mb-config
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Notes:

- Helm charts are tagged with Git release v2025.07.14 for production.
- Horizontal Pod Autoscalers for catalog-crawler scale based on Flux query latency metrics.
- All deployment units mount Vault Agent sidecars to retrieve dynamic credentials at runtime.
- Ingress TLS certificates are managed by cert-manager with ACME provisioning.

Appendix C – Test Case Coverage and Results

As of November 2025, the testing program encompasses 33 specified test cases. The test cases are described as follows:

Table 3 - Test cases

Test Case ID	Description	Category	Expected Result	Status
TC-01	Participant (Organization) registration at Authority Portal	Participant & Organization Management	Successfully validated organization and invited participant registration processes	Ok
TC-02	Person registration at Authority Portal	Participant & Organization Management	Confirmed new member access to Authority Portal dashboard with appropriate role assignment	Ok
TC-03	Organization Connector Registration	Participant & Organization Management	Verified connector appears as active in Control Plane dashboard	Ok
TC-04	Add connector with invalid/missing certificate	Security & Access Control	Confirmed proper rejection of invalid connector registration attempts	Ok
TC-05	Asset Registration (ingest CSV into)	Asset & Data Management	Successfully registered assets	Ok

	dataspace filespace: MinIO)		visible in asset index	
TC-06	Ingest CSV to Influx	Asset & Data Management	Validated data transfer to Influx DB	Ok
TC-07	Show charts on Influx dashboard	Asset & Data Management	Confirmed chart visualization on InfluxDB Dashboard	Ok
TC-08	Policy Definition (restrict asset to participants)	Contract & Policy Management	Verified restricted asset access	Ok
TC-09	Contract Definition (attach policy to assets)	Contract & Policy Management	Validated active and queryable contract definitions	Ok
TC-10	Contract Negotiation	Contract & Policy Management	Confirmed successful contract negotiation with valid agreements	Ok
TC-12	Data Transfer	Contract & Policy Management	Verified complete data transfer with integrity check validation	Ok
TC-13	Identity Management	Security & Access Control	Validated successful authentication and valid token reception	Ok
TC-14	API Security	Security & Access Control	Verified all unauthorized attempts are blocked while authorized requests succeed	Ok
TC-15	Control Plane Integration	System Integration & Discovery	Confirmed full integration with Control Plane features	Ok
TC-16	Crawler service running	System Integration & Discovery	Validated discovery and listing of all active connectors in network	Ok

TC-17	Crawler Asset Indexing	System Integration & Discovery	Verified complete index of all available assets across connectors	Ok
TC-18	Crawler Update Detection	System Integration & Discovery	Confirmed modified asset details are reflected in catalogue	Ok
TC-19	Metadata Semantic Search (UI)	Advanced Functionality	Validated accurate search results with proper filtering	Ok
TC-20	Metadata Editor	Asset & Data Management	Confirmed metadata editing	Ok
TC-21	Organization Registry Test	Advanced Functionality	Confirmed complete index of available assets across connectors	Ok
TC-22	User Management Deactivation/Reactivation	Advanced Functionality	Verified user operations are properly executed and persisted	Ok
TC-23	Asset Metadata	Asset & Data Management	Verified asset registration with complete metadata	Ok
TC-24	Hyperledger BESU Event Registration	System Integration & Discovery	Validated blockchain event registration functionality	Ok
TC-25	Metadata Ingestor	Asset & Data Management	Verified metadata ingestion processes fundamental to data workflows	Ok
TC-26	Vocabulary Hub Management (PoolParty)	Asset & Data Management	Verified vocabulary and taxonomy management for semantic search and standardization	Ok
TC-27	GraphDB Storage Test	Data Storage & Retrieval	Validated metadata storage and retrieval in GraphDB workbench	Ok

TC-28	Elasticsearch Indexing	Data Storage & Retrieval	Confirmed metadata is properly indexed and searchable	Ok
TC-29	MinIO S3 Storage	Data Storage & Retrieval	Verified files are correctly stored and retrievable	Ok
TC-30	Data Vault Security Configuration	Security & Access Control	Confirmed security controls are properly enforced	Ok
TC-31	Predictive Maintenance API Data Ingestion	Predictive Maintenance Integration	Confirmed data is correctly ingested and transformed	Ok
TC-32	Predictive Maintenance ML Predictions	Predictive Maintenance Integration	Validated models are correctly trained with expected performance	Ok
TC-33	Explainable AI results for Predictive Maintenance Predictions	Predictive Maintenance Integration	Validated production of results, stored on Influx DB	Ok